

Study on Laboratory Evaluation of Geriatric Anemia in a Tertiary Care Centre in Western India

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Abstract:

Background: People over age 60 are one of the risk groups for anemia. Anemia often leads to weakness and fatigue. Anemia in the geriatric population can be caused by various factors, including nutritional deficiencies (such as iron, vitamin B12, or folate deficiency), chronic diseases (like chronic kidney disease or cancer), medications, and bone marrow disorders. When geriatric population has these symptoms, it contributes to overall health decline. People having anemia might be less active physically.

Material and Methods: A prospective study was conducted among 1392 geriatric patients who attended clinic and were hospitalized between June 2023 to May 2024 in a tertiary care hospital whose blood samples and socio-demographic information were collected. Haemoglobin concentration, blood indices, RBC counts were determined by automated haematology cell counter. Grading was done according to WHO criteria and morphological typing was done on the basis of peripheral blood smear examination.

Result: A high prevalence (59.8%) of anemia was observed among 839 men commonly seen in age group (60-65 years). According to blood indices and peripheral blood smear analysis normochromic normocytic anemia (47.6%) was the commonest morphological type of anemia followed by hypochromic microcytic anemia (30.6%).

Conclusion: The present study concluded that management of geriatric anemia involves identifying and treating the underlying cause, which may include addressing nutritional deficiencies, managing chronic diseases, adjusting medications, and sometimes, administering blood transfusions or erythropoiesis-stimulating agents to boost red blood cell production. Regular monitoring and management of anemia are essential for the overall health and well-being of elderly individuals.

Keywords: Anemia, Geriatric.

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Introduction

Geriatric anemia, also known as anemia of the elderly or age-related anemia, is a common condition among older adults. It refers to a decrease in the number of red blood cells or the amount of haemoglobin in the blood in individuals typically over the age of 60. Symptoms of anemia in older adults can vary but may include fatigue, weakness, shortness of breath, dizziness, pale skin, and cognitive changes. It's essential for healthcare providers to evaluate and manage anemia in geriatric patients to improve their quality of life and prevent complications. Treatment may involve addressing underlying nutritional deficiencies, managing chronic diseases, adjusting medications, and, in some cases, administering blood transfusions or erythropoiesis-stimulating agents. Regular monitoring of haemoglobin levels and

addressing contributing factors are crucial for the effective management of geriatric anemia

Materials and Methods

The present study was carried out in the Central Clinical Laboratory (CCL), Department of Pathology, P.D.U Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, Gujarat, India for a period of 1 year between June 2023 to May 2024 which is a tertiary care hospital in western India.

Sample Size: A prospective study of 1392 geriatric patients who were hospitalized in a tertiary care hospital.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients having age more than 60 years and Patients with hemoglobin (Hb) less than 12 gm/dL.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients having age less than 60 years and patients with Hb more than 12 gm/dL. The clinical details were obtained from Central Clinical Laboratory requisition forms accompanying the blood samples.

The detailed history, clinical and physical examination and hematological investigations were performed. A total of 1392 random cases were studied. Blood counts were done by a 5part BC-6200 - Automated Haematology Cell Counter. Followed by peripheral smear examination. Differential count and red cell morphology were done manually by staining the blood smears with field's and leishman's stain. Following

investigations were carried out: hemoglobin, RBC count, WBC count, platelet count, hematocrit, Red cell indices, RDW, peripheral blood smear examination, reticulocyte count.

Results

Out of total 1392 geriatric patients most commonly affected age group was 60-65 years (59.6%) followed by age group 66-70 years (18.4%) .

The peripheral blood smear examination showed Normocytic Normochromic in 47.6% cases followed by hypochromic microcytic picture in 30.6% cases.

Figure 1: Age wise distribution of cases

Figure 2: Gender wise distribution of geriatric patients

Out of the total 1392 anemic cases, 779 are men and 613 are women.

Table 1: Distribution of anemic geriatric patients according to residence

Urban (%)	Rural (%)
20	80

1113 cases (80%) cases were of rural population while 279 cases (20%) were of urban population out of the total 1392 anemic cases.

Table 4: Red cell morphology on peripheral blood smear of geriatric patients:

RBC morphology on peripheral blood smear	Number of pregnant women	Percentage (%)
Normocytic Normochromic(NN)	663	47.6
Microcytic Hypochromic(MH)	426	30.6
Dimorphic anemia	246	17.6
Macrocytic	57	4.2
Total	1392	100

The commonest red cell morphology on peripheral blood smear was Normocytic Normochromic changes in RBC (47.6%) (Table3).

Discussion

Anemia in the elderly is a widespread global issue that is associated with poor clinical results. In spite of the fact that it is a severe issue that needs to be solved on a priority basis, especially in developing countries, it is most often ignored or sidelined owing

to the more pressing and demanding diseases in the geriatric patients. In the geriatric patients in whom there is a high prevalence of, neither the hemoglobin range nor the etiology of the disease causing anemia is easily recognized. This is an important setback because even mild anemia can hamper a patient's well-being, regardless of the underlying cause. Anemia occurring due to chronic diseases is the most common form of anemia in geriatric patients as observed in the present study.

Table 5: Comparative study of grading of anemia

Grade of Anemia	Present study (Rajkot, Gujarat) [2023] n = 1392	Abhishek Pathania et al (AIIMS, New Delhi)[2019] n = 229	Suma JK et al (Mysore) [2013] n = 114	Joosten et al (Belgium) [1992] n = 178
Mild (10–12gm/dl)	25%	47.60%	19.29%	29.2%
Moderate(7–10gm/dl)	49.6%	47.16%	16.7%	57.9%
Severe (<7 gm/dl)	25.4%	5.24%	2.4%	2.9%

Table 6: Comparative study of contributory causes resulting in anemia

Cause of Anemia	Present study (Rajkot, Gujarat) [2023] n = 1392	Nisha et al (Kozhikode, Kerala) [2017] n = 500	Joosten et al (Belgium) [1992] n = 178
Iron deficiency anemia	18.2	12.2	15
Anemia of chronic disease	57	48.9	41.5
Nutritional anemia	11	6.9	5.5
Blood loss	12.8	8.5	7.0
Haematological malignancy	0.7	18.5	11
Others	0.3	5	20

Grading: In this study, the highest number of patients is with moderate degree (Grade II) of anemia. This finding is similar to studies by Joosten et al. Our result differs from the studies conducted by Abhishek Pathania et al, in which the majority of the elderly had mild anemia (Grade I).

Age: In the present study, patients in the age group of 60–65 years were maximally affected, which is in concurrence with the studies by Amarneel et al, [6] Nisha et al, [9] and Kiran et al, [10]

Gender: In this study, more males were anemic as compared to females. Similar gender-wise findings were observed in the studies done by Khatib et al [4].

Cause: In this study, the most common cause of anemia is anemia of chronic disease. This finding is in concurrence with the studies by Nisha et al, and Joosten et al, in which chronic disease was maximally responsible for anemia followed by iron deficiency anemia.

Red cell morphology: On peripheral blood smear examination, anemia was classified into microcytic hypochromic, macrocytic, normocytic normochromic. Maximum cases of normocytic normochromic (47.6%) followed by hypochromic microcytic (30.6%), followed by Dimorphic anemia (17.6%) were observed.

Figure 3: Iron deficiency anemia - microcytic hypochromic red blood cells

Figure 4: Normochromic, Normocytic red blood cells

Figure 5: Peripheral smear showing Macrocytic anemia

Conclusion

The present study was done to evaluate the prevalence, type & cause of anemia in geriatric patients. Despite the advanced diagnostic advance available, geriatric anemia still happens to be under-reported and inadequately investigated, thereby evaluation of even mild anemias is important in this geriatric population. Symptoms like weakness and fatigue shouldn't be ignored or attributed to the normal aging process as it can be important symptoms to the presence of anemia. Improved definitions of anemia and more detailed investigations like bone marrow aspiration and biopsy helps to define the subtypes of anemia, thereby encouraging accuracy in diagnosis to ensure appropriate patient management.

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